

From Policy to Reality: Harnessing Data Spaces for Sustainable Urban Development

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and aims of the policy brief

The proliferation of detailed data—from satellite observations and sensors to Internet of Things and administrative registries— combined with the widespread adoption of analytical tools is reshaping how we understand and respond to ‘grand’ societal challenges. Climate change is one such challenge, and the European Union has committed through a suite of strategies and measures to becoming climate neutral by 2050 while adapting to environmental shifts already underway. Central to this effort is the recognition of data as a strategic asset. Building a single market for data is expected to unlock social and economic benefits, while supporting the ambitions of the European Green Deal.

Cities are at the forefront of this green and digital transition. Cities are mandated with direct service provision and implementation of European Union policies and regulations. Moreover, climate change is felt even more intensively in urban areas due to their morphology, density in population and built-up systems. In the past decades, cities achieved considerable progress in promoting innovative strategies to address environmental concerns, for instance, through the Covenant of Mayors¹ initiative. Yet cities have been grappling with leveraging data into policymaking. Despite numerous initiatives to promote data-driven transformation, often, whole-of-system approaches are still lacking. Besides patchy or unavailable data governance frameworks, cities face challenges related to data availability, quality and interoperability.

The European Union has mobilised with regulatory frameworks, standardisation efforts and research initiatives to encourage secure, trusted data sharing and use. Cities can tap into valuable resources including collaboration across European cities, exchange knowledge with key stakeholders, access funding and research to deploy context-based, sustainable solutions. Within the evolving landscape of data collaborations and technical solutions, data spaces are emerging as a promising model for facilitating collaboration across sectors and enabling data to be shared and reused in alignment with common policy goals.

This policy brief explores two complementary approaches or frameworks for data sharing and use that enable the collaboration between city-relevant stakeholders in the realm of environmental sustainability. Drawing on the examples of two projects outlined further—USAGE and SPOTTED—we aim to understand how technical arrangements and governance mechanisms can harness the potential of data integration to drive environmentally sustainable solutions. Together, these perspectives offer actionable insights for city leaders and policymakers seeking to translate data into tangible climate action. The brief concludes with recommendations grounded in real-world pilot experiences.

1.2 Significance of the USAGE and SPOTTED projects

USAGE (Urban Data Space for Green Deal) aims to enable universal access to city-level environmental and climate data for everyone, following the FAIR principles. Its objective is to support the European Data Strategy implementation and various priority actions of the European Green Deal, with a specific focus on cities and towns where the impact of climate change is most prominent.

USAGE offers innovative governance mechanisms, streamlined arrangements, AI-driven and other tools, and data analytics to facilitate the sharing, accessibility, and utilisation of city-level data. By leveraging data and service interoperability standards, USAGE strives to establish a decentralised infrastructure for collecting, processing, and exchanging reliable data, based on commonly agreed principles. This infrastructure aims to facilitate the combination

¹ Launched in 2008, the initiative is spearheaded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Energy and promotes energy and environmental sustainability among European municipalities and territories. For more, consult <https://eu-mayors.ec.europa.eu/en/about/objectives-and-key-pillars>

of diverse data sources, transforming them into decision-ready information for policy analysis and decision-making at large. To validate its solutions, USAGE conducts pilot projects in four distinct settings, showcasing the effectiveness and applicability of its approach.

SPOTTED (Satellite oPen data fOr smarT ciTy sERvices) aims to provide an innovative solution based on the integration and customised processing of massive Open Data collections, including Earth Observation data, to monitor and support decision makers in the field of green areas management. The ultimate objective is to show how this framework can generate innovation and large-value creation through the implementation of three pilots in Milan, Helsinki and Naples, focused on the monitoring and planning of green areas in the cities in relation to different factors.

Data provided by Open Data portals from the public administrations of the three cities, the European Data Portal and Copernicus, including real-time data captured by sensors, which are handled by means of the CEF Context Broker Building Block. Furthermore, relevant datasets generated by the Action will be made available itself through the European Data Portal.

2. THE POLICY LANDSCAPE FOR DATA-DRIVEN ENVIRONMENTAL ACTIONS

2.1 The European Union's framework for the twin green and digital transition

The European Union has, in recent years, placed a paramount emphasis on the effective utilisation, sharing, and overall optimal exploitation of data within its borders. This strategic focus underscores the European Union recognition of data as a critical asset in driving innovation, economic growth, and societal progress across its member states. To this end, a strong legal framework surrounding data has been developed through regulations such as the Data Governance Act, the Data Act, the Artificial Intelligence (AI) Act, and the Open Data Directive. All these instruments are valuable resources for implementing the broader European Union vision for the twin green and digital transition expressed in the European Strategy for Data² and the EU Green Deal³.

The **European Strategy for Data**, unveiled by the European Commission in February 2020, is a cornerstone of the European Union digital policy. Its primary objectives are to establish a unified data market across member states, promote data-driven innovation, and reinforce Europe's global competitiveness in the digital sphere. A key aspect of the strategy is its emphasis on enhancing data sharing among businesses, governments, and researchers while maintaining rigorous standards for privacy, security, and ethics. It establishes a cross-sectoral governance framework for data access and utilisation, with one of its central components being the development of common European data spaces in strategic sectors and domains of public interest. This investment aims to accelerate the development of the European digital economy and exploit the full value of data for societal benefit.

In the context of the European Strategy for Data, the European Commission introduced several regulatory mechanisms around data to address environmental concerns. The **Data Governance Act**, adopted in 2022 aims to facilitate data reuse by establishing a trustworthy and reliable framework for voluntary data sharing⁴. Through a number of horizontal measures, the Data Governance Act supports the creation and growth of common European data spaces, for instance, by facilitating the reuse of specific public sector data that cannot be made openly available⁵. It also regulates the role of data intermediaries, incentivising and simplifying the process of data exchange between data holders and data users (businesses, citizens). It is, therefore, expected to enhance cross-sector and cross-border data sharing, especially favouring local governments to collaborate more effectively with other municipalities, and regions on shared challenges, like the ones of climate change. Succeeding the Data Governance Act was the **Data Act**⁶ adopted in 2024 to promote data availability for innovative use in line with European Union rules and values. The Data Act aims to establish guidelines for increasing accessibility to high-quality data, thus promoting the development of a data market for new products and services. Among the several benefits, the Act seeks to empower users of internet-connected devices to access and share their generated data; enable public sector institutions to access private company data under specific circumstances (e.g. earthquakes, pandemics); and defines requirements for data interoperability in data spaces (DS) and for data-processing service providers.

Two other legal instruments that regard data for environmental purposes must be mentioned here: the **Implementing Act on High Value Datasets** introduced by the Open Data Directive in 2022 and the **INSPIRE Directive**. Based on six priority categories defined by the Open Data Directive⁷, a list of high-value datasets was identified to describe datasets

² European Commission. (2020). A European strategy for data, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. COM(2020) 66 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0066>

³ European Commission. (2019). The European Green Deal, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. COM(2019) 640 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52019DC0640>

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act). <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/868/oj>

⁵ Farrell, E. et al. (2023) European Data Spaces: Scientific insights into data sharing and utilisation at scale, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.

⁶ Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act). <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854/oj>

⁷ Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/1024/oj>

held by the public sector, including research data, whose reuse holds high potential of generating benefits for society and the environment. Opening and making available free of charge public sector information, in machine-readable formats, is a critical asset for common European data spaces as it allows the integration with other data sources to generate cross-sector insights and address interconnected challenges as those posed by climate change. Finally, the INSPIRE Directive entered into force in 2007 aims to establish a common European Spatial Data Infrastructure to support and improve environmental policymaking by specifying data provision requirements and introducing governance means to support higher efficiency in implementation (for more see Kotsev, 2023⁸).

In parallel, the European Union sponsors several initiatives - for coordination and support, deployment, research and innovation - to foster digital transformation through the creation of the Common European data spaces envisioned at strategic and legislative levels⁹. Right from the start, the common European **Green Deal Data Space** (GDDS) has been recognised as a cross-cutting key priority that intersects with other strategic areas such as health, energy, mobility, public administration and the European Open Science Cloud. Its primary objective is to leverage data potential in supporting key Green Deal initiatives by empowering a diverse range of stakeholders, including policymakers, businesses, researchers, and citizens, both within Europe and globally, to collaboratively address critical environmental challenges. Among other objectives, the Green Deal Data Space seeks to draft a set of rules of legislative, administrative and commercial nature that determine the rights of access to and use of data¹⁰. Various initiatives and projects have been funded to provide references for technical architecture, priority datasets as well as implementation tools like roadmaps and communities of practice to define and deploy the Green Deal Data Space (e.g. GreenData4All, The GREAT Project, AD4GD). Particularly relevant to mention here are the European Union **Data Spaces Support Centre** (DSSC) as a transversal initiative for coordination and alignment in the development of all sectoral data spaces; and the **Data Space for Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities** (DS4SSCC) that supports local communities and authorities to create added value from data sharing, contributing to sustainable actions.

All-above legislative initiatives demonstrate the Data Spaces Support Centre dedication to promote the power of data for societal and economic advancement while maintaining a framework of responsible and ethical data usage. Moreover, by promoting data accessibility and standardisation through flagship projects such as Data Spaces Support Centre, GREAT and Data Space for Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities, the European Union aims to provide guidance and resources to its member states in the building process of a more innovative and competitive digital landscape. On this background it is important to underscore the crucial role played by cities and local communities as both first-line legislative implementers and leaders in delivering the EU Green Deal ambitions through concrete actions¹¹.

Cities and municipalities across the European Union have been long engaged in developing climate and environmental policies, digital and data policies, and initiatives at the crossroads of the two policy areas. In other words, cities are both the sources of and solution to today's economic, environmental, and social challenges. However, cities are still lagging behind in framing data into policy practices and creating integrated systems that leverage available resources and existing stakeholder networks to address environmental challenges¹². Urban data spaces for Green Deal offer significant opportunities to European cities, enabling them to align their digital transformation efforts with environmental objectives, creating beneficial synergies between these two critical areas.

⁸ Kotsev, A., Minghini, M., Cefl, V., Penninga, F., Robbrecht, J. and Lutz, M., (2021) INSPIRE - A Public Sector Contribution to the European Green Deal Data Space, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.

⁹ European Commission (2024) Commission Staff Working Document on Common European Data Spaces, Brussels, SWD (2024)21 final.

¹⁰ European Commission (2021) Information session on a preparatory action for the common European Green Deal Data Space under the Digital Europe Programme' (DIGITAL), December 15th, 2021. Available online: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/events/information-session-preparatory-action-common-european-green-deal-data-space-under-digital-europe>. DG ENV (2022) The development of a European Common Green Deal data space. Publisher: EC and EEA INSPIRE Team. INSPIRE MIG/16/2022/DOC3

¹¹ Duriex, E., and Hidson, M. (2023) Local Green Deal. A Blueprint for action. The European Commission's 100 Intelligent Cities Challenge. European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency and DG GROW.

¹² Liva G, Micheli M, Schade S, Kotsev A, Gori M and Codagnone C (2023). City data ecosystems between theory and practice: A qualitative exploratory study in seven European cities. *Data & Policy*, 5: e17.

A data space approach provides a secure ecosystem to access comprehensive environmental data which has the potential to enhance, for instance, local administrations' decision-making processes by making more informed decisions, in areas such as urban planning, pollution control, and biodiversity conservation. By facilitating access to high-quality, interoperable data, local authorities can better tailor their offerings to meet citizens' needs, potentially leading to improved efficiency and higher levels of public satisfaction¹³. Moreover, by making valuable datasets freely available, local governments can demonstrate openness, build stronger relationships with their constituents, and encourage civic participation¹⁴. As we discuss further, a key premise of the Green Deal Data Space and other connected data space initiatives is the expansion from a technology-focused concept of the data space as a platform for data sharing towards ecosystemic approaches for which stakeholder participation, role and responsibility distribution and data value creation are crucial governance elements to consider for data space creation¹⁵. Despite being known concepts and practices to European cities, establishing urban data spaces for Green Deal presents advantages but also challenges that we closely examine in the next sections.

¹³ Klievink, B., Van Der Voort, H., & Veeneman, W. (2018). Creating value through data collaboratives. *Information Polity*, 23(4), 379-397.

¹⁴ Pereira G, Eibl G, Stylianou C, Martínez G, Neophytou H and Parycek P (2018) The role of smart technologies to support citizen engagement and decision making: The SmartGov case. *International Journal of Electronic Government Research* 14(4), 1-17.

¹⁵ Ponti, M., Maccani, G., Portela, M., Pierri, P., Daly, A. et al., (2024) Unlocking Green Deal data – Innovative approaches for data governance and sharing in Europe, Maccani, G. and Thabit Gonzalez, S.(editors), Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/0517622>

2.2 Data spaces as enabling ecosystems for urban sustainable development

In today's technology-driven world, data has become an indispensable resource for the effective functioning of the society. Its significance is particularly evident in tackling environmental challenges and global emergencies, boost sustainable growth, improve evidence-driven policy making, increase transparency, accountability and trust across society¹⁶. The European Green Deal sets an ambitious target of achieving climate neutrality for the EU by 2050. Governments at different levels play a pivotal role in this endeavour. At the local level, for instance, governments collect vast amounts of data related to different matters such as energy consumption, emissions, waste management, and environmental quality. Moreover, they hold knowledge and experience of collaborating with private, voluntary, research and education sectors that can provide cross-sector solutions to meet local needs. Data spaces have the capacity to create a holistic approach to data gathering and to bypass the obstacles often created by the fragmentation of data across different systems and sectors, both private and public, promoting better innovation in climate solutions. By focusing on the power of integrated data, European local actors can develop more resilient, efficient, and environmentally friendly cities, aligning their efforts with the broader objectives of the European Green Deal and global climate action initiatives.

The concept of 'data space' itself is not novel to field experts. Multiple public and industry-led initiatives have been promoting or piloting data sharing ecosystems (e.g. GAIA-X, Catena-X, Europeana, RealLab). To establish a common understanding, the Data Space Support Centre currently defines the **data space** as *an interoperable framework which follows common governance principles, standards, practices and enabling services that support trusted data transactions between participants*¹⁷. Rather than providing a detailed analysis of data spaces, our intention here is to examine how data spaces are relevant for, and interpreted by, cities and local communities in their endeavours to accomplish the Green Deal ambitions, thus an urban data space. To this end, it is useful to highlight the purpose of data spaces which is to overcome legal, organisational, semantic and technical barriers to data sharing by combining necessary tools and infrastructures and by means of common rules and standards¹⁸.

Looking more specifically at the concept of the urban data space, it is important to note it is not limited to data produced at the urban level, such as administrative data generated by the local city council or data from citizen science projects within the city. While such data is undoubtedly crucial for an urban data space, data originating from outside the city, relevant to its stakeholders, can be also part of it. This includes data about the city itself, such as weather, satellite data, as well as data useful to the city, such as data about similar cities. Therefore, to unlock the potential of data-driven innovation, the combination of various data sources and the collaboration of different organisations are needed¹⁹. Urban data spaces offer a promising solution both as a secure and controlled environment for exchanging valuable information but also as a framework for collaboration between various city-relevant stakeholders.

First, urban data spaces hold particular significance for local governments and municipalities. These entities amass and manage extensive datasets encompassing urban planning, public services, environmental monitoring, and citizen engagement. However, the full potential of such information often remains untapped due to existing silos approaches in the public administration that struggles to build cross-department infrastructure for data collection and exchange. The implementation of data spaces can significantly enhance inter-departmental collaboration in local governance. To dismantle information silos between various departments, a municipality can rely on the urban data space in which each department preserves sovereignty over its data while efficiently sharing information in an integrated system. For instance, seamless integration of traffic management data with urban planning initiatives becomes possible, leading to more holistic urban development strategies.

¹⁶ OECD (2025), "Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data in the Age of Artificial Intelligence: A Companion Document to the OECD Recommendation on Enhancing Access and Sharing of Data", [https://one.oecd.org/document/COM/DSTI/CDEP/STP/GOV/PGC\(2024\)/FINAL/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/COM/DSTI/CDEP/STP/GOV/PGC(2024)/FINAL/en/pdf)

¹⁷ Liva G, Micheli M, Schade S, Kotsev A, Gori M and Codagnone C (2023). City data ecosystems between theory and practice: A qualitative exploratory study in seven European cities. *Data & Policy*, 5: e17.

¹⁸ Farrell, E. et al. (2023) *European Data Spaces: Scientific insights into data sharing and utilisation at scale*, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.

¹⁹ Ryazanova, Olga, Pétercsák, Réka, Heaphy, Liam, Connolly, Niall and Donnellan, Brian (2016) *Perception of Value in Public-Private Ecosystems: Transforming Dublin Docklands through Smart Technologies*. Working paper for Thirty Seventh International Conference on Information Systems, Dublin 2016. Working Paper. NIRSA - National Institute for Regional and Spatial Analysis, Maynooth University.

Second, data sharing across different services empowers cities to optimise resource allocation and respond more effectively to local needs. Private sector data in this regard hold enormous potential for socially relevant purposes and which is often hard to access by public authorities. By defining a shared purpose and clearly demonstrating the (business) value of data exchange, urban data spaces can overcome trust issues and incentivize the involvement of private sector organisations. Furthermore, data spaces can facilitate the secure sharing of relevant information with citizens, promoting transparency and enabling participatory governance, therefore promoting more informed decision-making and more effective and targeted interventions, ultimately improving the quality of life of citizens. Finally, the holistic collaboration promoted by data spaces can also enable cities to share best practices, compare administrative boundaries, compare performance metrics, and coordinate actions, thereby amplifying their impact and learning from each other’s experiences.

As briefly mentioned earlier, there are multiple initiatives and resources supporting organisations aiming to exploit data-driven solutions to tackle grand challenges (e.g. IDSA, OASC). To analyse and interpret local experiences with a systemic approach to data sharing for Green Deal goals, in this paper we adopt a framework of analysis informed by the Data Space Support Centre blueprint. The Data Spaces Support Centre provides a foundational framework as a ‘living’ model for establishing data spaces, continuously updating its resources as various data space efforts evolve. The blueprint is a comprehensive set of guidelines, consisting of both technical and non-technical considerations with sufficient granularity for organisations building secure, interoperable, and scalable data ecosystems. Moreover, the Centre keeps a catalogue with current available initiatives for data space creation.

One of the key elements of the Data Spaces Support Centre model is the breakdown of the data space concept into more manageable components, i.e. building blocks. On one side there are the non-technical aspects of data spaces that cover business, legal, and governance dimensions. On the other hand, there are the technical requirements, which are modular, reusable components designed to facilitate the creation and operation of data spaces by ensuring interoperability, data sovereignty, security, and privacy (see Figure 1).

This division is useful for the forthcoming analysis as we will delve and provide insights on mechanisms put in place by loosely coupled organisations to govern their interactions as well as data sharing. While the Blueprint is constantly updated, it is worth mentioning that throughout the different versions both technical and organisational building blocks are expanded, integrating refined technical specifications, a clearer conceptual model, and alignment with recent European Union policies on data governance and digital transformation.

Data spaces therefore serve as catalysts for innovation, especially in climate solutions, by allowing controlled access to relevant data for different stakeholders such as researchers, businesses, and citizens. This open yet secure approach can lead to the development of new technologies and services that support climate mitigation and adaptation efforts and drive the creation of smart, sustainable solutions tailored to urban environments. They enable a more dynamic and responsive approach to urban climate challenges, allowing cities to adapt quickly to changing conditions and emerging technologies.

FIGURE 1: Overview of Building Blocks (DSSC, 2025)

BUSINESS AND ORGANISATIONAL		
BUSINESS	GOVERNANCE	LEGAL
Business model Use case development Data Space Offering Intermediaries & operators	Organisational form & governance authority Participation management	Regulatory compliance Contractual framework
TECHNICAL		
DATA INTEROPERABILITY	DATA SOVEREIGNTY & TRUST	DATA VALUE CREATION ENABLERS
Data models Data exchange Provenance & traceability	Identity & attestation management Trust framework Access & usage policies enforcement	Data, services & offering descriptions Publication & discovery Value creation services

3. EXPERIENCES OF LOCAL DATA MANAGEMENT ENVIRONMENTAL OBJECTIVES

3.1 An organisational and governance perspective on data spaces: the experience of USAGE project

Shifting from isolated data-sharing initiatives to a sustainable, systemic collaboration requires an agreed governance framework among interested parties that supports the functioning of a future data space. This framework must go beyond technical integration to address stakeholder coordination, access policies, and data management, ensuring a shared foundation for collaboration. This in turn, facilitates the development of products and services to carve out long-lasting opportunities, and possibly engage external users. Data space governance is best understood as a set of principles, rules, and decision-making processes that guide the involved actors in achieving a common-set purpose. A clear, shared purpose is essential not only for aligning stakeholders on operational principles but also for reconciling competing interests—particularly between public actors and private companies that own valuable data and may only be willing to share them under specific conditions. Effective governance mechanisms can help establish trust, define incentives, and create safeguards that make data sharing mutually beneficial while ensuring compliance with legal and ethical standards. Moreover, as multiple data sources become available, a shared purpose helps match data supply with demand, maximising the impact of pooled resources and driving greater public value creation²⁰.

The “living blueprint” of the Data Space Support Centre incorporates several of these elements within its ‘Business and Organisational’ building blocks. Alongside technical components, these elements define the operational part of the data space, ensuring that the model adds value, reduces costs, and complies with legal requirements.

The USAGE project offers a practical perspective on data space governance, particularly in the context of local governments. Across the four pilot cities, governance and business model components have been developed through a co-creation approach, bringing together multiple stakeholders. Notably, this process was initiated before the release of the Data Spaces Support Centre blueprint, yet the emerging governance elements closely align with its proposed model—highlighting the robustness and transferability of the USAGE approach.

Figure 2 captures the conceptual structure underlying the urban data spaces developed across the pilot cities. It shows how policy priorities, stakeholder needs, and technical components such as tools, algorithms, and datasets are linked through clearly defined use cases. These use cases form the operational backbone of each data space, grounded in real-world (environmental) challenges and implemented through a chain of processing steps, data requirements, and service delivery. Below is described the process that was followed by pilot cities to lay the groundwork for the preparatory phase of each data space.

- Defining local challenges and stakeholder needs. The very preliminary step in the process involved the recognition of current, most pressing **local climate challenges** and understanding **stakeholders’ needs**. This helped shape a general purpose for each data space;
- Aligning with the EU Green Deal. The general **purpose** of each pilot city data space was defined within the broader policy framework of the EGD. By engaging local stakeholders, a set of priority policy areas were identified around which data-driven solutions could be developed to support their implementation;
- Balancing policy and technical feasibility. Bringing together priority climate challenges and potential data-driven solutions requires the assessment of what is desirable from a policy perspective and what is technically feasible

²⁰ Fritzenkötter, J., Hohoff, L., Pierri, P., Verhulst, S., Young, A., & Zacharzewski, A. (2022). Governing the environment-related data space. Available at SSRN 4250166.

FIGURE 2: USAGE conceptual model

(e.g. available spatial data infrastructures, tools and datasets). This **contextualisation** step was crucial, as it ensured that the design of the data space was aligned with local **policy** priorities while remaining technically viable and for which use cases could be advanced.

- Developing use cases aligned with local priorities. **Use cases** were designed to address previously identified challenges, ensuring alignment with local policy priorities while also responding to existing investments and initiatives. Promoting use cases and applications that are responding to local policy processes enhances the strategic relevance of the data space. Additionally, city administrations have been already piloting and experimenting with data-sharing solutions (e.g., open data portals, citizen science) which can be leveraged and integrated to strengthen the legitimacy, feasibility and sustainability of data spaces.
- Prototyping and testing tools and services to provide solutions that comply with FAIR principles and aim at bringing societal and business value.
- The developed process served as a blueprint model for the USAGE pilot cities and offers a practical and scalable approach that can be replicated by other cities seeking to develop their own urban Green Deal data space. In the next section, we delve deeper into the experience of Ferrara in designing its urban data space.

Ferrara’s approach to structuring the urban data space for climate challenges

Ferrara is one of the four USAGE piloting sites working on establishing an urban data space to support Green Deal-related policy actions. Its experience offers a valuable example of how middle-sized cities can approach the preparatory phase of a data space, particularly regarding non-technical elements.

It is important to note that Ferrara’s local authorities have a long track record of climate and data policy initiatives over the past decade²¹. These initiatives include common technological layers, such as a city open data portal and the recent geoportal for data visualisation, as well as collaborations with various non-governmental stakeholders focused on sustainability. However, at the outset of the USAGE project, there was no unified policy for automatic and secure data sharing across all levels or for ensuring interoperability between data sources and tools. In response, the municipality of Ferrara has taken a leading role in promoting a data space approach, building on its extensive knowledge and practical experience with local data sharing and re(use) with different stakeholders.

²¹ Van Ooijen, C. and Oprea, N. (eds.) (2023) D2.1 Challenge-led system maps. Available online: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1y9ufB3EZd7aEaKTS1WfIJRRRQPmLo56/view>

From EU Green Deal priorities to local climate challenges and needs

In recent years, Ferrara has been proactive in addressing the climate challenges affecting its territory. In the preliminary phases, three key EGD policy areas were identified as the most pressing local climate challenges and related city priorities:

- Climate actions related to mitigation and adaptation, such as urban heat islands, access to green spaces, floodings;
- Supplying clean, affordable and secure energy;
- Preserving and restoring ecosystems and biodiversity.

These policy areas represent starting points for aligning local resources and data needs with the broader objectives of the EU Green Deal. The projects the municipality of Ferrara is pursuing to mitigate and adapt to these climate challenges aim to improve the urban environment and advance the EGD locally.

The municipality of Ferrara, through its relevant departments, has adopted various Action Plans that draw from policies in the area of climate and environment, as well as data strategies functional to guide digital and technological innovation leveraging data accessibility and (re)use. In pursuing these policy goals, the municipality must engage with numerous local and regional stakeholders, from setting the policy agenda down to implementing evidence-driven actions. For example, regional agencies in Emilia-Romagna collect and provide relevant data for the municipality to carry out climate actions. One key example is the environmental and climatic data collected at the local level by the Regional Agency for Prevention, Environment and Energy of Emilia-Romagna (ARPAE). Similarly, private actors and research entities generate data on various city-related environmental and socio-economic topics (precipitation, energy services, water drainage, mobility).

By adopting a co-creation approach, the engagement of local actors brought to light various needs of legal, organisational, informational and technical nature. More specifically, city stakeholders expressed the need for a clear framework (legal rules, agreements) of automatic and simple data exchange. Relatedly, the need for investments to increase and consolidate civil servants' set of skills on data analysis for both ex-post and forecast analysis were noted. From a technical point of view, stakeholders emphasised the need for data exchange platforms, use of data standards and procedures, including protocols, and enhanced metadata quality to ensure not only access but also integration with other platforms. Finally, for the available data, interpretation and contextualisation emerged as an informational need, which requires the involvement of researchers and citizens. On this backdrop, establishing an organisational and technical model for interaction between various stakeholders seemed to be an answer to current issues, including assistance with high-quality data collection, streamlining data sharing across different (climate) themes, leveraging advanced analytical tools, and creating a clear configuration for stakeholder engagement.

Building the value proposition of Ferrara urban data space: use cases

Within the three identified EGD policy areas, a process of brainstorming and reviewing local policy programmes led to the development of various use case scenarios. Use case scenarios served as exploratory instances to envision how data and tools could be deployed in real-world operational settings. At preliminary stages, as outlined by the Data Spaces Support Centre, such scenarios allow stakeholders to consider planned or envisioned applications of data sharing.

In the Ferrara pilot, the stakeholders explored different use case scenarios, which ultimately resulted in four concrete use cases: two contributing to the climate action challenges, one focusing on energy, and one on biodiversity challenges. These use cases represent practical applications of the potential of data to accomplish stakeholders' jointly defined goals, thus contributing to co-creating business, societal or environmental value from data sharing. A key consideration in the maturation stage from use case scenarios to use cases was the reusability of existing datasets and tools— either publicly or privately held— to enhance the future effectiveness of the data space.

Although the use case technical descriptions fall outside the scope of this document, below is an overview describing the distinctive features of the use cases: their expected value; and their beneficiaries.

- Mitigating the impact of urban heat islands. This use case focuses on reducing the effects of urban heat islands, a phenomenon where some urban areas, especially highly built-up ones with altered natural environments, experience higher temperatures than their surroundings. Through a number of modular services, this use case integrates multiple data sources (satellite data, aerial hyperspectral images) to generate both a city-level vulnerability thematization (low-resolution) and street-level simulations of potential interventions (high-resolution). More specifically, it enables a vulnerability assessment based on simulations incorporating the population distribution and socio-economic information that can help identify priority neighbourhoods for which regeneration interventions are needed. These functions are delivered through visualization (e.g. interactive maps) publication services as open data and data stories, serving multiple users and information needs. Local decision-makers can tap into the potential of this use case to define problematic areas and design data-driven recommendations for urban regeneration measures, potentially combined with other services. Citizens and private actors can use interactive visualisations to propose solutions that could be used in policy actions. Moreover, the output services will allow us to build a common understanding of climate issues and the real needs of the community/neighbourhoods.
- Supporting the flood emergency response phase. Community engagement plays an increasing role in sustainable action plans, especially by citizens' and volunteers' ever active role as data collectors. This use case leverages bottom-up data collection campaigns, allowing citizens and volunteers to report and map flooded areas in real time via mobile applications. Citizen science campaigns have earned traction lately as valuable tools for engaging the general public in scientific research and gathering large amounts of data across wide geographical areas that would be otherwise difficult or expensive to obtain through traditional methods. Using mobile apps, volunteers can capture various types of data, such as images, videos, and geolocation data to report sudden changes in climatic events such as flooding. Once integrated, all collected data sources allow for the application of algorithms to detect flooded areas and calculate polygons representing flooded areas on a map. The service presents various unique advantages. It offers the local administration near real-time information to deploy responsive measures in disaster management. Moreover, compared to large-scale data acquisition campaigns, utilizing volunteers significantly reduces the costs of data collection. Environmental organisations can act as intermediaries to facilitate the participation of a large number of data collectors, while also disseminating the awareness of both environmental and data-related challenges.
- Incentivizing renewable energy sources. A cornerstone of the EU's climate neutrality strategy is the decarbonisation of various domains of human activity by transitioning from fossil fuels to renewable sources of energy. On this backdrop, it becomes highly relevant for local administrations to rely on services that estimate energy potential in the context of sustainable city development and support private initiatives. This use case provides a support tool to identify areas where installing photovoltaic (PV) panels would be most effective due to maximum solar irradiation. Through a number of modular services, the use case delivers different layers of maps displaying optimal areas, as well as their classification - best to worst - for PV installation based on energy production potential. It also provides information needed for estimating yearly energy production potential per pitch or pitch fraction. The service provides evidence-based support to urban planners to design policies, regulations and incentives that promote solar energy adoption. Furthermore, utility companies, businesses and citizens can use the information to make informed investment decisions to maximise solar energy yields.

A governance framework for Ferrara urban data space

Ferrara's urban green deal data space evolved from early informal consultations—exploring prospective members' needs—to a formal agreement among committed members. An important milestone in this evolution was marked by the “Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) for the activation and development of the Urban Data Space for Green Deal” approved by Ferrara City Council in 2023. The MoU foresaw the definition of first datasets for the DS and the ‘rules’ of exchanging and using data between the parties of the data space. The initial step regarded the provision of data interchange protocols and data interchange agreements.

In 2024, a legal expert appointed by the municipality drafted the first statute formalising Ferrara's commitment to the data space creation. This multilateral agreement sets the foundation for participation by constitution members and potential key stakeholders, including academia, enterprises, and public entities engaged in urban climate objectives. Ferrara's urban DS aims to go beyond the limitations of traditional open data—enabling more advanced analytics to uncover patterns, support strategic decision-making, and tangible value for participating members.

The municipality coordinates and steers the data space with the aim of creating a permanent infrastructure to the benefit of different internal departments and a framework for engagement with city-relevant stakeholders. Governance is entrusted to a Steering Group (Cabina di Regia) composed of founding members from the public sector (local and regional), private enterprises, the university and community organisations. The Steering Group is responsible for defining the strategy and priorities of the data space, monitoring, member coordination and regularly updating the technical annex of the agreement. Through a consensus-driven process, the founding agreement defines the rules of members' participation, their roles and responsibilities and the onboarding process of new members. The data space infrastructure is designed as a robust, scalable and trusted platform. It supports efficient data collection, management, and analysis—details of which are laid out in a dedicated technical document. It is worth mentioning that the technical annex provides various solutions and speaks to specific stakeholders' needs collected in the beginning of the process related to formats, models and protocols for interoperable data exchange. Ferrara's approach aligns closely with the broader principles of data space governance discussed earlier—grounding them in local realities through legal, organisational and technical instruments.

In the short run, the members expect to convert data collection and exchange into a more efficient and optimised process thus reducing processing time, while improving resource and task allocation, among others. A spillover effect of this transformation is better data quality, the proliferation of standards and specifications (catalogues, connectors, data), integration of multiple sources of data. In the long-run, constituent members expect to contribute to an enhanced process of environmental, health and social policy definition and implementation, as well as consolidate trust among current and future members. The general public and citizenry as whole may expect a more accountable administration, with transparent decision-making processes, and become active contributors both as data generators and data users.

3.2 A technical perspective on data spaces: the experience of SPOTTED Project

In the context of smart city services, as argued earlier, the data space approach is particularly relevant because it enables the seamless integration of diverse data sources—such as environmental sensors, urban infrastructure data, and geospatial information—into a unified framework. This integration is crucial for optimising urban planning, improving public services, and supporting sustainable development, all of which are key components of a smart city's ecosystem. By leveraging data spaces, cities can enhance their ability to make informed, data-driven decisions that contribute to the overall efficiency and livability of urban areas.

This section will explore how the solution developed within the SPOTTED project, despite it not being expressly conceived as part of the Common European data spaces scheme, has an architecture that can help build the technical layer of a Urban Data Space for Green Deal. The achievements of the SPOTTED project, with its platform and pilot results, align well with the Data Spaces Support Centre framework of enhanced building blocks, showcasing how a data-driven system can contribute to urban green data spaces. Moreover, as shown in the next section, SPOTTED’s emphasis on stakeholder engagement, iterative development and participatory design embodies the co-creation approach, providing a practical example of how co-creation can enhance the technical elements development in data spaces.

Technical building blocks include various aspects such as data federation, secure data exchange, and standardised interfaces, crucial for enabling different systems and organisations to interact within a data space. The Data Spaces Support Centre emphasises the importance of these building blocks in creating cohesive infrastructures that integrate diverse data sources and systems, ultimately enabling efficient and secure sharing of data across sectors. SPOTTED leverages satellite open data for smart city services, with a specific focus on urban green area management. The project has developed a platform that integrates satellite data with other open data sources to support urban planning and decision-making in three pilot cities: Milan, Naples, and Helsinki.

The SPOTTED Digital Platform is centred on the integration and processing of diverse datasets—especially satellite and geospatial data—into actionable digital services tailored to urban needs. It includes various components such as the CEF Context Broker, Idra, and other data management tools, which together enable the processing of large datasets in a way that supports policy and decision-making.

FIGURE 3: Overview of SPOTTED

For instance, the SPOTTED Platform allows cities to measure specific indicators, such as Milan's focus on Natural Capital and Health, by collecting, analysing, and delivering information via an open data portal. The processed data is then published in the European Data Portal as an open dataset, making it accessible for broader use. This process not only meets the technical specifications of a data space, but it also reflects the Data Spaces Support Centre's value creation focus by enabling urban stakeholders to make data-driven decisions.

- The Data Spaces Support Centre defines data spaces as federated and interoperable environments that allow data to be shared and utilised across different sectors and stakeholders securely and efficiently. SPOTTED's components, especially its data federation capabilities and its use of the CEF Context Broker, can serve as technical building blocks within this framework:
- **Data Federation:** The Idra platform within SPOTTED enables the federation of different open data portals, which aligns with the Data Spaces Support Centre's requirement for data spaces to connect and harmonise data from diverse sources. By using Idra to federate these diverse datasets, SPOTTED ensures that cities can aggregate and synchronise their data in a standardised manner, facilitating broader interoperability and scalability within the data space.
- **Interoperability:** The use of the Data Model Mapper ensures that data from various sources can be transformed and aligned with the specific data models required for different services, supporting the interoperability principle emphasised by the Data Spaces Support Centre. The Context Broker manages real-time information gathered by sensors, ensuring that data from heterogeneous sources like public administration portals, the European Data Portal, and Copernicus can be seamlessly integrated and processed. This capability is crucial for supporting the kind of dynamic, interconnected data sharing envisioned by the Data Spaces Support Centre, where different types of data need to be harmonised and made available.
- **Processing and Analysis:** The Processing Subsystem within SPOTTED, which automates the workflow from data collection to analysis and ultimately to publication in the European Data Portal, represents a key functional component that can be integrated into broader data spaces to facilitate the processing and utilisation of urban data. This system not only processes raw data but also ensures that the final datasets are stored securely and made accessible through standardised interfaces.

By enabling the creation of Digital Services and data visualisation for municipalities, SPOTTED also plays a crucial role in value creation. Now that we have reached the end of the project, SPOTTED has demonstrated its potential to transform diverse data sources—such as satellite imagery, NDVI analysis, and local open data—into actionable insights for urban planning, environmental monitoring, and climate adaptation.

FIGURE 4: Architecture of SPOTTED

For instance, in Helsinki, the project has focused on creating time series analysis to track green areas and assess urban heat impacts, combining these data with population metrics to better understand the pressure on green spaces. These positive outcomes highlight how SPOTTED can provide cities with the tools needed to make informed, data-driven decisions, which are essential for achieving sustainability goals.

Similarly, in Naples, the pilot has shown how SPOTTED can enhance urban green capital strategies and support sustainable energy and climate action plans by offering detailed analyses of vegetation health. The discussions in Naples also explored new use cases, demonstrating the flexibility and scalability of the SPOTTED platform to address various urban challenges.

These results illustrate SPOTTED’s potential to support the creation of data-driven smart cities by providing the necessary infrastructure for the integration and utilisation of diverse datasets. This capability aligns with the Data Value Creation principle emphasised by the Data Spaces Support Centre Blueprint, making SPOTTED a key enabler in the development of interoperable, scalable, and sustainable Urban Data Spaces. As the project continues to evolve and expand its services, its impact on urban governance and environmental management is expected to grow, further solidifying its role in the future of urban data ecosystems.

SPOTTED and Co-Creation in Data Spaces

Co-creation in the context of data spaces emphasises the collaborative involvement of stakeholders throughout the design, development, and operational phases, ensuring the resulting solutions address real-world needs and challenges effectively. One of SPOTTED’s central strategies was the formation and maintenance of Pilot Local Groups (PLGs) across its three pilot cities—Milan, Naples, and Helsinki. These groups brought together diverse stakeholders, including public administration representatives, technical experts, and local organizations, to guide the project’s development. This collaborative framework fostered an active partnership around shared goals and values.

During the project's early stages, SPOTTED employed innovative engagement methods such as reverse pyramid skimming and snowballing techniques to ensure broad participation while refining the group to include the most relevant stakeholders. These approaches supported the co-creation process by incorporating diverse perspectives, fostering trust, and encouraging iterative feedback loops. In Helsinki, the inclusion of local experts in the early phases facilitated the development of new services, such as time-series analyses of green areas, that directly addressed urban planning needs.

The co-creation methodology was further evident in SPOTTED's emphasis on continuous stakeholder engagement during the design and assessment of its digital services. This phase highlighted the importance of balancing innovation with feasibility, ensuring that proposed solutions were not only creative but also technically and economically viable. Namely, the SPOTTED team used interactive demos and mock-ups to engage stakeholders, allowing them to visualise the platform's potential and provide actionable feedback. This participatory approach ensured that the platform's services, such as the Urban Green Index and heat exposure analysis, were tailored to meet local users' needs.

Moreover, SPOTTED's two-step approach to co-creation exemplified the Data Spaces Support Centre Blueprint's emphasis on structured and inclusive processes. By first working with technical experts to identify feasible solutions and then involving stakeholders in refining and selecting these options, the project created a dynamic feedback loop that enhanced both the quality and relevance of its outputs. This method also allowed for the integration of local expertise with cutting-edge technology, a hallmark of effective co-creation.

In the later phases, SPOTTED continued to prioritise stakeholder input during the platform's experimentation and dissemination stages. For example, workshops and live demonstrations were used to showcase the platform's functionalities, enabling users to test the system in real-world scenarios and suggest improvements. The lessons learned from these activities informed further refinements, ensuring the platform remained user-centric and adaptable.

SPOTTED's commitment to co-creation extends beyond its immediate project scope, offering a replicable model for future urban data space initiatives. Its emphasis on iterative engagement, collaborative service design, and user-focused development, report a vision of data spaces as participatory ecosystems that drive innovation and address societal challenges. By embedding co-creation at its core, SPOTTED not only delivers impactful solutions for urban planning but also advances the broader objective of creating inclusive and sustainable data spaces.

4. POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR LEVERAGING DATA FOR URBAN SUSTAINABILITY

In this final section, an outline of general lines of action are proposed for city leaders and policymakers in general engaged in exploiting data potential and related services to tackle environmental challenges. The experience of the USAGE and SPOTTED projects with their multiple pilot sites show that both technical and non-technical aspects are crucial to deploy systemic data collaborations.

Cities are uniquely positioned at the intersection of data creation, service delivery and citizen engagement. However, they often lack institutional support and resources to develop digital data tools to serve their environmental challenges. European Union strategies, plans and regulations, as previously examined, represent a **framework** that cities can leverage **to drive investments in environmental and digital initiatives**. More specifically, cities and local communities, besides complying with European Union directives and regulation, such as Data Governance Act or the INSPIRE Directive, can benefit from their application by expanding access to more sources of quality and trustworthy data, including proprietary data, and re-use them to develop better service offers. At the same time this also requires that national and European Union frameworks **recognise cities as key actors** in the emergent European data ecosystem and provide targeted instruments to support their roles of data creators, stewards, and re-users.

Meanwhile, cities should explore various **platforms for cooperation** (e.g. Copernicus, European Environmental Agency platform) built around the European Union regulatory framework to gain visibility and participate in European funding projects. Likewise, cities would benefit from joining EU Missions or key associations at European level (e.g. ICLEI, OASC) to receive technical support while accomplishing climate-related commitments. For instance, the **Community of Practice** of the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change can be used to exchange knowledge and collaborate with other cities dealing with similar climate adaptation challenges and use valuable insights on policies at the service of ecological transition.

Many European cities have subscribed to reach climate-neutrality, restore biodiversity or transition to clean energy, by setting ambitious targets which require credible and trusted data sources for baseline measurements and monitoring of implemented actions (e.g. emissions inventory). To this end, **adopting systems thinking** allows cities to move beyond fragmented and individual data flows towards shared data infrastructure that addresses the variety of data formats, standards and licences used by organisations and improve the knowledge among urban initiatives. Embracing a **data space** approach in the context of implementing the EU Green Deal at urban level offers a promising solution both as a **secure and controlled environment** for exchanging valuable information but also as a **framework for collaboration** between various city-relevant stakeholders.

One important challenge faced by cities and the local city administration is the scarce levels of resources and skills to integrate data into a shared infrastructure and combine multiple data sources to tackle local climate challenges. Urban data spaces can be seen as an enabler of moving beyond municipal departmentalisation and postulate solutions that address real user needs. One USAGE pilot city showcased the approach of conceiving an urban data space in which municipal entities and departments retain sovereignty over their data while efficiently and safely sharing information in an integrated system. Local administrations should promote a **broad alliance across relevant departments** (e.g. urban planning, information systems, environmental and infrastructure) which serves to jointly define a common purpose for the data space and agree on specific standards and models for data use and exchange.

Likewise, small and middle-sized cities often lack the technical and analytical skills to make full use of satellite, sensor-

based on Earth observation data, including environmental and climate assessment skills²². To bridge this gap, the SPOTTED project developed a Processing Subsystem that automates the workflows and provides cities with pre-analysed, readily accessible data aligned with specific urban needs. Moreover, collaborative efforts between various organisations involved in an urban data space allows to **tap into different types of expertise and knowledge** as the case of university and research organisations. For instance, the inclusion of local experts in Helsinki in the early phases facilitated the development of new services, such as time-series analyses of green areas. While in Ferrara, the involvement of university researchers has supported the interpretation of thematic data analyses for hydraulic risk management. While ad hoc technical solutions can support short-term needs, a long-term strategy should include **investments in digital skills** among municipal staff, especially related to data integration, prediction modelling and interpretation.

The involvement of the community and city-relevant stakeholders in an urban data space should go beyond mere consultation, it should focus on co-defining the common purpose and the **expected value** of the data space. As discussed in the case of Ferrara pilot, establishing a **governance framework** was key to clarifying participants' roles and responsibilities, onboarding procedures of new members and the technical parameters for data collection and use in the data space. Once the purpose and the principles of the data space are established, member participants should **identify practical applications** of the potential of data to accomplish stakeholders' jointly defined goals through use cases. Participants of urban data spaces should **deploy pilots around use cases** in which the value of the entire data value chain is clear to all stakeholders. An 'experimental' approach to piloting use cases can show what will work, for whom and under what circumstances and early on decide on the usefulness of use cases. Co-creation is one approach to engage participant members or most relevant stakeholders. For instance, in the SPOTTED Project, Pilot Local Groups (PLGs) were formed and maintained in a stepwise manner to ensure constructive engagement while understanding users' needs, expectations and design accordingly services that balance innovation with feasibility (technically, economic).

Finally, data spaces offer an opportunity to move beyond traditional models of open data publishing (i.e. data space 1.0), toward a more nuanced approach that treats data as a strategic resource (data space 2.0). This includes exploring mechanisms for the controlled use of closed or proprietary data and enabling value creation through products and services built on top of shared datasets. Crucially, this shifts the paradigm toward a demand-driven approach, where the utility of data is measured by how it contributes to solving specific urban challenges. The focus must therefore be on **how data is used**, not just how it is shared.

²² European Investment Bank (2023) The state of local infrastructure investment in Europe EIB Municipalities Survey 2022-2023.

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